

GAME THEORY IN DECISION MANAGEMENT

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Abstract

Purpose - This article presents the applications of game theory in management decision making.

Methodology / approach - The methodology proposed in this article is based on the use of game theory for control and decision making in economics. Predictive methods are applied for urban transport planning, and their results contribute to measuring decision-making performance.

Findings - Based on the experiments performed by the authors, an application on traffic prediction was developed and tested within the Department of Intelligent Transport Systems of UPB, for the planning of urban passenger transport.

Research limitations / implications - The paper offers a concrete solution obtained at the department level. This solution based on the implementation of the game matrix is a new approach to urban transport planning in accordance with ITS requirements.

Practical implications - The practical aspects approached by the authors are related to the identification of the best balance matrices with intelligent agents for the implementation of urban transport planning management, using a new methodology based on game theory.

Originality / value - The methodology based on the algorithm-oriented approach of game theory for predicting urban traffic planning can be implemented for measuring, evaluating, and improving traffic using ITS strategies.

Key words: management, decision, game theory

Introduction

In recent years, there has been a growing interest in the use of game theory algorithms implemented with intelligent agents for the development of software systems to assist in decision-making and agent-based management systems. Prediction and decision making theory is based on a set of mathematical algorithms for making decisions and generating strategies that can be applied if the results of potential actions are unknown.

Game theory developed long before the advent of the concept of "smart agent", agents are examples of software applicability for decision makers who can combine the classical theory of decision making with Artificial Intelligence algorithms.

The interactions between game theory and prediction theory

In general, decision / prediction theory is a way of analysis, which needs to choose a predefined scenario, when the result is not known after choosing a working scenario. Decision theory focuses on identifying the best choice of "decision", accepting the condition that the notion of "best" can have several different meanings, of which the most used decision is to maximize the final planning result that the decision maker and proposes it.

Game theory studies the aspects of how interaction strategies between individuals can be developed to maximize the well-being of an agent in a multi-agent interaction, but also how protocols or mechanisms of interaction with properties can be developed. imposed by the decision maker. It can be noticed that the theory of decision is considered as the study of game theory (survival) against nature, where nature (environment) is an opponent who does not want to get the best compensation, because he has a chaotic behavior.

Based on the above, we find that many applications based on game theory with implementation on multiagent systems (experts) have been developed for the analysis of events such as negotiation and coordination / planning.

The concept of decision prediction has evolved from the concept introduced by Michael S Scott Morton (2015) to the decision management system based on intelligent agents. In 1980, Sprague defined Decision Support System (SSD) as "interactive computer-based systems that will help decision-making management use data and predictive models to solve problems." This definition was pro-active, which is why the definition was generalized to include all systems involved in prediction and decision making (Sprague R, 1980).

The extension of the initial definition led to the hiding under the name of SSD of different types of systems, many of them having nothing to do with the initial idea of SSD. Initially, these were tools aimed at large companies, but in recent years SSDs have become important and accessible tools for small companies. The existence of these tools has changed and will continue to change the way we make decisions. They allow the individual or organizational decision maker to manage the volume and complexity of information more efficiently and to better coordinate activities.

Circumstances of group decision making

In most cases, SSDs are developed and implemented in companies in all fields of activity. Although most companies have a hierarchical leadership, decision making is a collective process. The decision-making group can be involved in making the decision, but the decision can also be made by a single person, such as creating a short list of alternatives or choosing the criteria for accepting an alternative.

The main purpose of the SSD system is to use appropriate mechanisms (analysis of data, documents or calculations and predictions) to provide support in making the right decision for a situation imposed by certain situations (Filip F, 2004). The correct decision can be taken only after a careful analysis of all possible results obtained, taking into account all the factors that may influence the decision-making act and following the analysis performed by all parties involved in the management process.

The decision is the result of the analysis actions for choosing an optimal direction of action, which often involves the allocation of new resources. The prediction obtained from the processing of information and databases, which may belong to a person or a group of people, with the necessary authority, is ultimately used by decision makers in certain concrete situations (Parson S, 2002). A complex decision-making environment creates the necessary framework for the use of decision-making software applications. Research and case studies analyzed by us have shown that a well-designed and structured IT system to support decision making, can improve the quality of the managerial decision and can increase the efficiency and effectiveness of the management process.

Today, computer systems have become a powerful tool to help in decision making. Decision makers work better with the relevant information obtained in the shortest time. Effective support decisions can give managers greater independence in retrieving and analyzing data (Big Data), thus obtaining quality information and desired results. The decision-making process can take place based on a well-defined "scenario", which can be formulated tangentially with the rules of a game in the concept of "Game Theory" (depending on the field of applicability) through the following stages:

- Strict determination of all parties involved in the decision-making process (persons or groups of persons);
- Defining the possible actions (scenarios) that each party participating in the given process can undertake;
- Establishing the rules of the evaluation "process" (evaluation stages and existing priorities);

- Establishing the criteria according to which the evaluation will be made, and the respective decision will be adopted;
- Creating a list of alternatives and choosing the criteria for predictive alternative;
- Creating compromises and balancing interests or creating coalitions in case of need (imposing these compromises if necessary);
- Distribution of results according to the defined criteria (directing the gains according to the adopted decision).

Given an individual "scenario" of negotiation between agents (decision makers), various techniques in the field of game theory can be applied, which refer specifically to the definition of the protocol "rules of negotiation". Protocols can have certain predefined (default) properties are:

- guaranteed success.
- Maximizing social status.
- Efficient Wall.
- Individual choice.
- Stability of choice.
- Simplicity of the solution.
- Distribution of the decision.

Users & beneficiaries

Among the most important aspects that must be highlighted during the design stage of a SSD are the establishment of the user and the beneficiaries for whom the respective system will be destined, as well as the fields of use and the way of functioning it. Regardless of whether a single person or a group of people will participate in the decision process, systems must satisfy the essential characteristic which consists in: "providing support and improving the way of human judgment, control of the system, the system thus remaining entirely under the control of the user" (Holis S, 2001).

Thus, Sprague (1980) defines five categories of roles of people involved in the process of design (construction) and use of SSDs, taking into account the classification of SSDs in terms of technological levels (specific SSDs, SSD generators, SSD tools):

- Managers / decision makers (users) - the person who will make the decision and will be responsible for the consequences of the choice made
- Intermediaries - the person who helps, to a certain extent, the manager in using the support system for specific decisions and in choosing the decision by providing suggestions
- SSD Builder / Facilitator - the person who designs / builds / configures the specific SSD using an SSD generator. The builder must have knowledge both in the field of decision making and technical knowledge
- Technical support staff - develops new features for SSD, as component parts of the SSD generator (databases, analysis models, new presentation elements)
- SSD instrument developer - develops new technologies, new languages, new hardware and software components to improve the connections between subsystems.

According to Sprague, 1980, a person can assume one or more roles, depending on the nature of problems, and the level of technical academic background and the orientation of the person. Filip (2004) regroups these roles in 3 categories:

- Users - all those who are in direct or mediated interaction with SSD, to form a decision-making unit in the elaboration and adoption of decisions
- Intermediaries - make the connection between users and developers of SSD instruments in the activities of transition from instruments to customized systems (builders-specialists) or to mediate or facilitate the use of application systems (intermediaries of use)

- SSD tool makers - specialists who develop decision-making methods and those who implement associated IT products, including SSD generators.

Areas of application (meaning, context, purpose)

The classical models of game theory have found their applicability during the last decades in different social fields to the analysis of some problems with decision-making or conflicting character. The most common are applied to issues in the field of economics, management or marketing, but also in socio-political issues of a voting nature. It applies to various social methods in which there is usually no independent "fake" choice that one can make - in which the "best" results depend on the actions of the other participants (Hollis M, 2001).

In game theory, the consequences refer to the values that each participant receives as a result of the choices made by both him and his opponents. The consequences are often represented by numerical values; these numerical values can be represented discretely - matrix, or continuously. A key concept in game theory is the criterion of optimality. It refers to the rational decision in which a setup of movements is designated to bring an optimal reward, even after evaluating all possible movements of appearances. In game theory, the concept of the game solution of two or more people means a situation of balance for all players. The crucial issue is how to adapt the classic mosquitoes from game theory to various decision-making problems in different social, economic, political fields. Simultaneously with the choice of the appropriate model for the problem in question, it is very important how to determine the solution and the correct interpretation in terms of the respective field.

Research Methodology: The use of game theory and intelligent multiagent in transportation planning

The proposed method is based on game theory and the implementation of Intelligent Multiagent Systems (SMA). Each agent has an associated utility function. The values of this function are represented in a payment matrix that is known by both agents included in the negotiation. Each agent also appreciates an alternative law that will maximize its usefulness. Although the method based on game theory is simple and elegant, it has very strong restrictive assumptions that make it difficult to apply to practical situations. Real-world negotiations take place in conditions of partial or complete uncertainty, include multiple criteria that cannot be synthesized by a utility function alone and the utilities of agents are not known, so agents are not omniscient (all-knowing). Another way to allow an agent to learn and use an evolutionary algorithm. They are based on the biology, deriving from the theory of evolution through natural selection. The most commonly used algorithm of this type is genetic algorithm (GA).

It works with a population of individuals, each with a certain measurable level of "fitness" using a metric defined by the model builder.

The most representative individuals are "reproduced" by multiplying with other people who are adapted to the process, and by multiplying them result descendants who have characteristics taken from both parents. Multiplication continues over time, over several generations, which will lead to a state of mobility of the population as the population evolves and adapts to the environment. In the case of neural networks and genetic algorithms, the software developer must make a decision on the conditions imposed on the development model. For example, in the case of models based on genetic algorithms, it can be considered that a single agent can represent the entire population. The genetic algorithm will become a "black box" used by the agent for learning and adaptation in the environmental conditions imposed by the developer. Alternatively, each individual can be programmed as an individual agent, and the result obtained will be a population of intelligent agents interpreted as a whole in the process of evolution. Similarly, we can program each individual agent or groups of agents with neural networks, and each development environment (economy) and society to be represented as a single neural network, each neuron being assimilated with an agent (for this situation it is difficult to built all the attributes of the agent).

Figure 1. Implementation of game theory for the selection of bus destination

Implementation of the SMA algorithm and game theory for urban transport

One of the simplest but most effective ways to develop agent-based models is to use a production system algorithm. A production system algorithm has three components:

- multiple rules;
- dynamic working memory;
- a set of prediction rules.

The established rules have two fundamental parts: a set of conditions that specify when the imposed rules will be enforced and when the planned actions will be carried out. For example, an agent may be designed to walk in a simulated environment to purchase any food he encounters in the action. Such an agent will work according to the rule: If I come across a food WHEN I buy it. This would be one of the rules, and each rule in the instruction set will have a different condition. Some rules may include actions that present facts that exist in the collective memory of the agent community, and the conditioning rules will have the role of testing the collective memory. The set (database) of rules analyzes each rule in turn, chooses the rules for which most conditions are met and performs the specified actions, repeating this cycle an unlimited number of times. Different rules can be executed for each action cycle, because the environment changes after an executed rule changes the collective memory, so that new rules for the functioning of the population are generated. Using a production system algorithm, it is easy to build and introduce in the community intelligent reactive agents that respond to external environmental stimuli through actions. It is also possible, but more difficult to achieve agents who may have the ability to think (reflect) on the action of the environment, and the decisions made to shape their knowledge. Another possibility for development is to build agents who create their own rules (learn on their own) using an adaptive algorithm that favors effective actions and can sanction other members of the population. This is the basis of classification and decision systems.

Agents designed on the basis of the production algorithm have a high potential to adapt and analyze their environment and can develop new rules adding knowledge to the collective memory of the population (action memory). To solve certain problems, it is necessary to create intelligent agents capable of learning on their own: so that the internal structure and processing of the rules always adapt to the environmental conditions, which are dynamic. In order to achieve the conditions for the adaptation of agents to the environment, they can be developed on the principle of functioning of neural networks, because they are closest to the human thinking mechanism.

Figure 2. Development adaptive algorithm for bus destination (for the morning hour interval)

Figure 3. Development adaptive algorithm for bus destination (for the evening time slot)

In this context, the designed cognitive architecture of an agent can be defined as the part of the system that provides and manages the agent's primitive resources. Cognitive architectures usually fold on an information cycle that begins with receiving information by monitoring the execution environment, continues with filtering and processing them, memorizing relevant knowledge, making a decision based on current status and previous experience and ultimately involves taking action. . A system that implements such an architecture should be able to perform a diverse range of cognitive tasks, using a number of problem-solving and information representation methods, and be able to learn as many aspects of work tasks as possible, and of the success of their fulfillment. Theoretically, with an architecture for general intelligence, any aspect of intelligence would be studied, the system should be able to model it within the considered structure.

Conclusions

Game theory is often found as an analytical tool for solving problems in various fields of activity and is a practical guide to model application strategies in specific areas (management, economics, or policy development by governors). The conditions of game theory are rarely approximated in real life.

Game theory and intelligent agents are algorithms used in prediction and decision-making processes, allowing the development of mathematical models for solving real problems. Prediction and decision making is of great importance in managerial activity in all areas of activity. ITS professionals have to make daily decisions on traffic management, they use both quantitative methods of analysis, but not least prediction software applications. Intelligent transport system managers apply game theory methods developed based on intelligent agents to solve problems and plan traffic problems.

The activity of managers in traffic planning is based on estimating the parameters of the evolutionary game matrix using different methods of implementation with intelligent agents. The main result of the research in this article is the application of game theory and smart agents to traffic planning and in the previous paragraphs we showed how real-time data can be correlated with historical data obtained in different time periods. To achieve very good results for modern traffic planning, software developers use quantitative and qualitative models of smart agents, along with game theory and evolution.

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